

Monopoly and Pricing of Options: A Quantitative Model

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Abstract

Monopoly is a form of institution: the pre-requisites regarding this form of companies is that prices are dictated by the capital makers, however in our finding we have argued about the behavior of monopolistic companies regarding the derivatives markets, Futures for instance; first of all we can swiftly show that once in a time the expectations of companies for the general price under a suitable filtration must be higher even though this price itself isn't high if the monopoly form would be great for customers, namely what is the behavior of monopolies to avoid raising prices in the Future, this went to consider that since they have a higher expectation for general prices they must long Futures contracts.

The Option on Futures Market was the target of our study, we have been interested in the behavior of such a market under this situation where the only form of companies operating in the country is monopolies, with our empirical study we have shown bluntly that under a monopolistic environment the *Option on Futures Market* is cheaper and behaves almost like the Crude Oil WTI Futures, we have taken our price and Futures data from investing.com. The research question lies in defining a new insight in a big government economy where monopolies come to rein in dictating prices, our finding is crucial because the *Option on Futures Market* could be a solution for traders when the economy doesn't allow competition.

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1 Introduction

The pricing theory is full of mysteries and whereabouts, this article is a great work on behalf of statistical economics and the theory of price; we suppose our economy is monopolistic in which case the only form operating for the economy is monopoly.

We had statistically shown that for prices to avoid being raised by big monopolies, there should be some fairness in their expectations, our intuition seems to lack exactitude, the estimator $E[p_t/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$ is a biased estimator which means that expectations of monopolies as we would show later on should be high under the universe H even though the real value of p_t is not as high as expected, policy makers could force this company's behavior by enforcing a general panic to manipulate future prices pushing demand to be low, customers have the right to spend more while being immune from losing their purchasing power.

The research question was to find a market that could be a scapegoat for protecting demand to rise and descend abruptly, we had studied the *Option on Futures Market* carefully and after calibrating our model we discover that this market is cheaper than Futures Market of oil, our target was the Crude Oil WTI Market because of its omnipotence to cover all the economical framework, our finding is always statistical, we can see later on that both Crude Oil WTI Futures and the corresponding *Option on Futures* analogue trace the same history of prices.

Spulber Daniel F. (2002) has studied *Monopoly Pricing*, he had demonstrated that Nonlinear pricing is almost optimal for the monopolist as the number of customers was important, Pekka Sääskilahti (2007) had discussed the monopoly typology and social interactions under a device characterized by asymmetric information. Our study has shown alike that monopolies can be a lever for derivative Markets, the *Option on Futures Market* was showing weakness under a monopolistic situation which means a lot that whenever prices are rational, it takes more for monopolies to operate with ease.

2 Model

Sometimes statistics can serve new concepts even though they are not very used in the scientist literature, Suppose we operate in a monopolistic environment and that the only form of companies is monopoly, our vocation is to guess that even though prices are dictated by companies for this special patent as monopolies, there is an invisible power governing the setting of prices by monopolistic companies; let's suppose under the space $(H, \Omega, \mathcal{F}_t)$ which is the right space for which prices are not raising in a monopolistic

situation.

$$\begin{aligned} p_{t+1} &= E^H[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] + \epsilon_{t+1} \\ E^H[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] &= \alpha p_t \\ r_{t+1} &= (1-a)r_t + ab + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

Where $\frac{dH}{dP} = \alpha \frac{p_t}{p_{t+1}}$ and $\alpha \leq 1$, r_t is the interest rate at time t , $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$, we would study the case $\alpha = 1$ closely to find out a restriction on the behavior of monopolies so that prices would be stable over time.

$$E^H[\alpha/\mathcal{F}_t] = E^H[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] E\left[\frac{1}{E^H[p_t/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}] + \epsilon_t} / \mathcal{F}_t\right]$$

For $E^H[\alpha/\mathcal{F}_t] = 1$, which means that monopolies won't rise prices and the economical paradigm at best must be the same.

$$E^H[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-t(\mu - t)) dt$$

Where $\mu = E^H[p_t/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$

$E^H[p_t/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$ must be higher which means that it is a biased estimator for p_t if a monopolistic market is willing to avoid rising prices, indeed the real value of p_t is small because $E^H[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = \alpha p_t$ and $E^H[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t]$ is an unbiased estimator of p_{t+1} .

To enforce expectations of companies for p_t to be high unions must encourage customers to reduce their demand abruptly which is a logical action that goes in accordance with prices rigidity in the market, if expectations of monopolistic companies about price are high they would long Futures contracts which gives

$$F(t, T) = E^H[p_T/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

Which is a mispricing in the Futures Market, as this estimator is biased as we had shown previously. In order to correct such an inefficiency in the Futures Market, a current sell or buy of Futures would be conveniently appropriate for this matter, it is namely a pledge for paying back a loan at the current time at the future rate that we might expect as $E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t]$ under the risk neutral probability Q^* .

This might correct this mispricing in the essence which means that a statistical sense or a logical correlation exists between Futures at the coming time $t + 1$ and the expected short rate $E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t]$.

$$F(t+i, T) = p_t + \delta^i E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

We might estimate $\hat{\delta}$ using the first *écriture* of Futures as the following

$$p_{t+1} = p_t + \hat{\delta} E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

Which means clearly that

$$\hat{\delta} = \frac{p_{t+1} - p_t}{E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t]}$$

Afterward we are going to perform Option on Futures pricing using our model, the calibration of both Futures and Options on Futures would follow

$$C_t = E[\exp(-\int_t^T r_s ds)(F(T_1, T) - K)^+/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

We consider a sample $(r_t)_{t \geq 0}$, which means deterministic rates to get our calculus simple.

$$E[F(T_1, T)\mathbb{1}_{F(T_1, T) \geq K}/\mathcal{F}_t] = E[(p_{t+m} + \delta^m E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t])\mathbb{1}_{F(T_1, T) \geq K}/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

On the other hand

$$\begin{aligned} E[p_{t+m}\mathbb{1}_{F(T_1, T) \geq K}/\mathcal{F}_t] &= p_t Q^*(F(T_1, T) \geq K) + E[\sum_{i=1}^m \delta E^{Q^*}[r_T/\mathcal{F}_{t+m-i}]\mathbb{1}_{F(T_1, T) \geq K}/\mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= (p_t + \sum_{i=1}^m \delta(1-a)^i r_{T-i} + \delta \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} ab(1-a)^j) Q^*(F(T_1, T) \geq K) \end{aligned}$$

3 Calibration of the model

We need to calculate the probability $Q^*(F(T_1, T) \geq K)$ for this reason we suppose prices are ruled by the simplistic stochastic equation

$$p_t = p_{t-1} + \sqrt{h_t} \epsilon_t$$

Afterward

$$Q^*(F(T_1, T) \geq K) = Q^*(\epsilon_t \geq \frac{K - p_{t-1} - \delta^m E[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t]}{\sqrt{h_t}})$$

We need afterward to estimate the future expected rate with respect to the current information \mathcal{F}_t , we have

$$E[r_T/\mathcal{F}_t] = (1-a)^n r_t + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} ab(1-a)^j$$

The values a and b were assigned fair values when we had experienced our data for several times, the calibration argument was though so weak in that regard, a lack of data was a burden to estimate all the parameters.

As for the variance we had taken the serie of prices in *investing.com* and made a code to calculate the serie of variance, to be honest we could have supposed a model for volatility, however there is no need for as this latter doesn't appear in calculous unless for the calculation of $Q^*(F(T_1, T)) \geq K$.

the *Option on Futures model* against Futures Market values

Conclusion: the *Option on Futures Market* of oil under a monopolistic economics behaves almost like its Futures analogue and is indeed cheaper than the futures Market, our argument was though weak regarding calibration as it seems like trivial to take on modeling without fair exactitude, we have shown almost that any derivative Market can be modeled swiftly without calibration, any other argument can take our study to Hartford.

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